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Shaping the
digital future of
catalysis

<https://nfdi4cat.org/>

Dear reader,

a lot has happened since the last newsletter. The most exciting thing was probably our Annual Meeting, the ADCR22, which took place in September. Apart from the stimulating discussions and scientific exchange, the poster session and inspiring international lectures were the highlight of the event. We would like to take this opportunity to thank all participants for their contributions and support!

You can read about these news and get more updates in our newsletter below!

We hope you enjoy reading it,

Your NFDI4Cat management team

ADCR 2022 – NFDI4Cat partners and exhibitors

What would life be without good partners and supporters? An event like the ADCR lives on the fact that many people help and support us. In this context, we would like to introduce our NFDI4Cat partners who helped us make the ADCR22 a success.

NFDI4Chem, FAIRmat, Daphne4NFDI, NFDI4DataScience and OntoCommons joined us with an exhibition booth that attracted a lot of interest from the visitors attending the event.

ADCR22

NFDI4Cat
NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences

Partners & Exhibitors

nfdi4cat.org

#ADCR22

Learn more about our partners!

ADCR 2022 – Presentation and Keynotes

NFDI4Cat organizes the ADCR to showcase our latest results and, more importantly, our goals for the coming year. However, the main theme of this event is digital catalysis and research data management. This year's ADCR featured some great presentations from industry and academia on this topic from different perspectives, turning the event into a hub for innovation.

Would you like to learn more about our invited speakers?

Yes, absolutely!

ADCR 2022 – Poster Prizes

The ADCR22 provides the opportunity to present and discuss new and innovative topics not only in the form of keynote presentations, but also in the form of posters. NFDI4Cat aims to motivate young academics and young professionals from industry to contribute to research data management in catalysis by awarding four poster prizes, including a Twitter prize for the best contributions. We warmly congratulate all winners and thank all participants for their scientific contribution!

ADCR22

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POSTER Prizes

nfdi4cat.org

#ADCR22

Let's take a look at the winners!

Events

NFDI SCIENCE SLAM – DATA SCIENCE and AI – Learn more [here](#)

Lighthouse RDM: Orientation in the flood of data - Get informed [here](#)

56. Jahrestreffen Deutscher Katalytiker - [Find out more](#)

NFDI4Cat - Book recommendation

Good Data: An Optimist's Guide to Our Digital Future

Sam Gilbert

This book offers a critical but optimistic overview of digital technology and the data revolution. Sam Gilbert provides a clear and sensible account about data outlining the significance of sharing it and making it available. He also points out the benefits of collecting and aggregating big data sets for

public policy and even presents a framework for data governance.

[I want to read it!](#)

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